

Performance of DSM walls on shoring excavation subjected to influence of nearby high building loads and rapid drawdown in the lower mainland, Vancouver, BC

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ABSTRACT

The use of deep soil mixing (DSM) as a method of shoring for excavations is a common practice in engineering. This study presents a finite element 2D model in Plaxis to analyze the support of a 4.3 m excavation for a new high-rise development using a DSM wall reinforced up to a depth of 10m, while the rest remains without reinforcement up to another 22 m below ground level. The design of the DSM wall aims to protect the excavation against ground collapse from the self-weight and the presence of a 16-storey existing high-rise building. To consolidate the ground, stone columns were constructed up to the less permeable soil layers for soil densification, and a preload height of 3.5m was applied. The DSM wall was numerically designed with respect to the superstructure, consolidation settlement for the soft clay layer, and the rapid drawdown during the excavation process. Additionally, the horizontal deflection and vertical settlement of both the excavation wall and the high-rise building were analyzed based on different water content for DSM cement mixing with two target layers viz., the loose sand and clayey silt. The study provides valuable insights into the design of DSM walls for excavations, taking into consideration various factors that can affect the stability of the structure.

1 INTRODUCTION

Deep soil mixing (DSM) is a popular ground improvement technique used to enhance soil properties and increase soil strength. DSM walls have been used in numerous civil engineering projects for excavation support, foundation construction, and environmental remediation. The use of DSM walls can help to reduce permeability, increase stability, and prevent seepage in soil conditions where conventional construction methods are not feasible. However, DSM walls can also face challenges in certain soil conditions, such as those with seepage, ground heaving, and the presence of loose sands and silts. Previous studies have investigated the performance of DSM walls in challenging soil conditions. A study by Han and Ye (2002) evaluated the effectiveness of DSM walls in preventing seepage in a riverbank. The study found that the DSM walls were effective in reducing seepage, but that the design of the wall and the binder type and dosage were

RÉSUMÉ

L'utilisation du mélange de sol profond (MSP) comme méthode d'étayage pour les excavations est une pratique courante dans l'ingénierie. Cette étude présente un modèle 2D à éléments finis dans Plaxis pour analyser le soutien d'une excavation de 4,3 m pour un nouveau développement en hauteur à l'aide d'un mur DSM renforcé jusqu'à une profondeur de 10 m, tandis que le reste reste demeure sans renforcement jusqu'à 22 m sous le niveau du sol. La conception du mur DSM vise à protéger l'excavation contre l'effondrement du sol dû au poids propre et à la présence d'un immeuble de grande hauteur de 16 étages présent depuis environ 50 ans. Pour consolider le sol, des colonnes de pierre ont été construites jusqu'aux couches de sol les moins perméables pour densifier le sol, et une hauteur de précharge de 3,5 m a été appliquée. Le mur DSM a été conçu numériquement en ce qui concerne la superstructure, le tassement de consolidation pour la couche d'argile molle, et l'abaissement rapide pendant le processus d'excavation. En outre, la déflexion horizontale et le tassement vertical du mur d'excavation et de l'immeuble de grande hauteur ont été analysés. L'étude fournit des indications précieuses sur la conception des parois DSM pour les excavations, en tenant compte de divers facteurs susceptibles d'affecter la stabilité de la structure.

critical factors in achieving optimal performance. Similarly, a study by Rutherford et al. 2007 investigated the use of DSM walls for excavation support in a site with loose sands and silts. Yapage et al. 2014 studied the effect of soft ground on the performance of DSM walls. Other studies have focused on the use of quality control measures during DSM wall construction. A study by Ishibashi et al. (2017) investigated the use of a continuous mixing method for DSM walls to improve quality control and ensure the uniform distribution of the binder. The study found that the continuous mixing method was effective in achieving consistent binder distribution and that the resulting DSM walls had higher strength and durability compared to those constructed using conventional methods. Despite these findings, there is still a need for further research to address the specific challenges posed by the effect of water content in the DSM mix for cohesive and non-cohesive materials.

Overall, the literature suggests that DSM walls can be an effective solution for challenging soil conditions, but that careful consideration must be given to factors such as soil type, binder type and dosage, mixing depth, and quality control measures during construction. The findings of this paper contribute to this area of research by presenting a comprehensive evaluation of DSM wall performance in an excavation project with seepage, ground heaving, and loose sands and silts, providing valuable insights into the factors that contribute to successful DSM wall construction in these conditions.

2 METHODOLOGY

In this study, the soil is modeled using 15 noded plain strain elements in Plaxis 2D. The soil layers used in the simulation are representative of those typically found in the Richmond area near the Brighthouse Station. The soil layers include a top layer of fill, followed by layers of loose sand, clayey silt, and a compact layer of sand. Since the loading is static in nature and the problem is not expected to undergo large deformation, a simple Mohr-Coulomb material model is used for all the soil layers. The analysis also considers possible consolidation of all the soil layers. The DSM column is designed such that each cylindrical column has a diameter of 0.6 m and an area of mutual overlap. The center-to-center distance between the DSM columns is considered as 1.3 m. In each alternative column, an I section reinforcement is considered to better resist the flexural load from the soil layer and the nearby structures. Table 1 provides more details about the reinforcement design.

The DSM section is checked against moment and shear resistances based on Figure 1, but these details are not explained in detail in this paper for the sake of brevity.

Figure 1. Details of the DSM wall configuration showing the cross-section of the DSM mix and the I section reinforcement in alternate columns.

Table 1. Details of the I section used for the reinforcement of DSM walls.

Metric	Depth (mm)	Width (mm)	Thickness (mm)	Web thickness (mm)	Section Modulus (mm ³)
460 × 260	509	289	40.4	22.6	5650

The DSM walls in this study are modeled as elastic plate elements, incorporating appropriate interface elements. The elastic modulus (E value) for the DSM walls is determined based on the recommended value of 380 times (as per the FHWA for Embankments and Foundations, 2013). This value ensures an accurate representation of the stiffness and behavior of the DSM walls in the analysis.

2.1 Stages of construction

The construction process for the study can be divided into eight stages. The detailed stages are described in Table 2 and also the important stages are shown from the Plaxis model in Figure 2. Stage 1 involves establishing virgin soil conditions with zero displacement. In Stage 2, the high-rise building is constructed. Once construction is complete, Stage 3 begins, which marks the end of consolidation at the position under building load. Stage 4 is reached at the end of consolidation after preload. In Stage 5, preload removal is complete, and consolidation continues. At this point, the lateral deflection and vertical settlement values are determined. Stage 6 marks the end of the first stage of excavation, while Stage 7 marks the end of the second stage of excavation. Stage 8 includes the end of the third stage of excavation and final consolidation. The lateral deflection and vertical settlement values discussed in the results and discussions section were measured at the end of consolidation, which is at the end of Stage 8. These stages provide a clear timeline for the construction process and help to contextualize the findings of the study.

Table 2. Stages of construction followed in the tests

Stages	Description
S1	Establishment of virgin soil conditions (zero displacement)
S2	Construction of the high-rise building
S3	End of consolidation the position under building load
S4	End of consolidation after preload
S5	End of Preload removal+ End of consolidation after preload removal
S6	End of first stage of excavation
S7	End of second stage of excavation
S8	End of third stage of excavation + final consolidation

Figure 2. Model diagrams in Plaxis showing (a) preloading after construction of the DSM wall, (b) excavated section and steady state removal of water.

2.2 Material Properties

The material properties of the soil layers are presented in Table 3. The soil layers are composed of a medium dense sand fill, clayey silt which has relatively low cohesion and low friction angle, followed by loose sand and followed by a till-like layer which here is presented as a compact sand.

Table 3. Strength properties of the soil layers

Characteristics	Sand Fill	Clayey Silt	Loose Sand	Compact Sand
Young's Modulus, E in kN/m^2	71.3e3	21.45e3	25e3	85e3
Poisson's Ratio	0.30	0.39	0.31	0.29
Liquid limit	3	35	-	3
Plastic limit	-	22	-	-
Friction angle ϕ in $^\circ$	32	22	30	36
Dilation angle ψ in $^\circ$	1	0	0	3
Cohesion c in kPa	0	20	0	0.5

2.3 Variation in stratigraphy

Assuming that the typical DSM wall extends approximately 50 m across the plane, it is reasonable to assume that the two critical layers, Loose Sand and Clayey Silt, will vary across the site. In order to model the soil profile in 2D, Table 4 describes the possible different sections that need to be considered. Cases 1, 2, and 3 consider the depth of the Loose Sand layer to be 0.6 m, 1.6 m, and 2.6 m, respectively. Cases 1, 4, and 5 capture the variation in the Clayey Silt layer at 3.1 m, 4.1 m, and 5.1 m, respectively. It should be understood that the variation in these important layers might significantly affect the serviceability of the DSM wall and, therefore, must be considered in the analysis. Specifically, the variation in these layers might affect the lateral movement of the DSM wall, its settlement, and the settlement of the 16-storey building with a total uniform load of 210 kN/m^2 , which is assumed to be at a fixed distance of 7 m from the excavation.

Table 4. Soil stratification considered in the current study

Soil layers	Top ¹ (m)				
	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5
Sand Fill	0	0	0	0	0
Clayey Silt	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8
Loose Sand	3.9	3.9	3.9	4.9	5.9
Compact Sand	4.5	5.5	6.5	5.5	6.5

¹Difference between top of each layer gives layer thickness. Case 1 to 3 assumes variations in the Loose Sand layer across the site, whereas Case 1, 4 and 5 represents changes in the Clayey Silt Layer.

Figure 3. Variation of compressive strength of soil-cement mix at the end of setting for (a) sand, (b) clays (modified from Topolnickli 2016)

2.4 Water content

Apart from the variation in the thickness of the soil layers, it is also important to focus on the water content of the design mix which uses soil from these layers to prepare the DSM wall. It was pointed out by Topolnickli (2016), that the effect of water content on the 28 day Uniaxial Compressive Strength (UCS) of sands are different from that observed in clays when they are mixed with cement. Figure 1 shows that increase in the total water content TWC can significantly and monotonically decrease the UCS values

of concrete when sand is used in mixed design for DSM walls. This trend is different in clays, where increase in WC might increase the UCS value up to an optimum maximum value in the mix strength is obtained beyond which there is steady decline in its strength. In the current study, we assume that the design of the DSM walls will involve different combinations of the WC in the loose sand layer and the clayey silt layer. The WC in the fill and the compact sand layer are considered as constant. It is interesting to note how the DSM wall bends inwards from the combined effect of excavation and the lateral force exerted by the 16 storey building. The values of UCS can be usually connected with the Young's Modulus E value of a DSM deep-mixed material empirically as 380 times the UCS value of the specimen (Topolnickli (2016)),

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The investigation focused on the construction of the Deep Soil Mixing (DSM) wall and subsequent excavation. The variation in the soil profile across a 50 m out-of-plane length excavation was captured using five different 2D plane strain sections, namely Case 1 (Sand & Clay), Case 2, Case 3, Case 4, and Case 5. These variations had significant effects on the lateral deflection (u) of the DSM wall nearest to the high-rise building, as well as the settlement of the high-rise building (v).

Figure 4. The deformed mesh showing the lateral deflection of the DSM wall and the vertical settlement of the close building. Note : Settlements are exaggerated 50 times for better visualization

Figure 5 illustrates the lateral deflection of the DSM wall at the top right corner, providing insights into the behavior of the wall under different scenarios. An envelope of curves was plotted, considering variations in water content exclusively for the sand layer. It was observed that there exists a monotonic, almost power-law relationship between the increase in total water content (TWC) and the lateral deflection. For instance, at TWC = 20%, the u value was found to be 53 mm, while for TWC increased to 32%, the u value increased significantly to 94 mm. This trend closely aligns with the decrease in compressive strength observed

in cement-sand mixtures as TWC increases, as shown in Figure 3. However, as the thickness of the loose-soil layer increased, as represented by Case 2 and Case 3, the deflection exhibited a gradual increase but appeared to saturate after a certain depth. In the case of clay layers, there seemed to be a specific design TWC that resulted in the least effect on the u value. Moreover, the impact of TWC on the reduction of the u value was relatively lower when compared to the loose sand mix. Furthermore, the influence of increased clay layer thickness, as depicted in Case 4 and Case 5, exhibited diminishing effects on the u value. The changes in u became progressively lesser as the clay layer thickness increased. Understanding these settlement patterns is crucial for the design and construction of structures in similar geotechnical conditions. It allows engineers to anticipate and mitigate potential settlement issues, enabling the development of more robust and resilient foundation systems for high-rise buildings.

Figure 5. Lateral deflection of the top right corner of the DSM wall in response to varying water content in the DSM cement-soil mix design for loose sand and clayey-silt layers.

Figure 6 illustrates the impact of changes in the unconfined compressive strength (UCS) of the soil mix and the increased consolidation resulting from the heightened clay layers on the settlement of the left corner of the high-rise building. These settlement observations are a consequence of the excavation and redistribution of in-situ stresses.

The influence of UCS reduction on the vertical settlement (v) of the building is prominently observed in the sand layer, where consolidation has no effect. The settlement in this layer is primarily governed by the reduction in UCS. However, the behavior of the clay layer differs, as it deviates from the initial loss of strength curve, which exhibited an inverted "V" shape. As the thickness of the clay layer increases, the settlement of the building due to layer consolidation becomes more significant than the loss of lateral stress caused by the excavation.

Figure 6. Vertical settlement of the left corner of the highrise building in response to varying water content in the DSM cement-soil mix design for loose sand and clayey-silt layers.

These findings highlight the contrasting behaviors of the sand and clay layers. The sand layer primarily experiences settlement driven by the reduction in UCS, whereas the clay layer exhibits settlement influenced by both consolidation and lateral stress reduction. The deviation from the original loss of strength curve suggests the complex interaction between the clay layer and the surrounding soil during the excavation process.

Overall, the results demonstrate the significant influence of soil variations on the behavior of the DSM wall. The relationship between water content, soil layer thickness, and lateral deflection provides valuable insights for the design and construction of DSM walls, highlighting the importance of considering these factors to ensure the stability and performance of such geotechnical structures.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a comprehensive analysis of the Deep Soil Mixing (DSM) wall construction and its interaction with the surrounding soil and nearby high-rise building was conducted using Plaxis 2D fully coupled simulation. The construction process was divided into eight phases, including wall preparation, preloading, and excavation of the inner soil in three stages. The variability in the soil layers around the site was carefully considered, focusing on two critical layers: loose sand and clayey silt. Five different sections were analyzed, accounting for the variations in these target layers.

The results of the study revealed that the water content and differences in thickness between the sand and silt layers significantly influenced the performance of the DSM wall. Specifically, the lateral deflection of the wall and settlement of the nearby high-rise building were found to be greatly affected by these factors. The lateral settlement primarily resulted from unloading due to excavation, while

consolidation of the silty clay layer played a relatively smaller role.

Furthermore, the settlement of the high-rise building was influenced by both the excavation process and consolidation of the soil layers affected by the excavation. In sections where the thickness of the silty clay layers exceeded 2 m, vertical settlement was predominantly governed by consolidation rather than the effect of the DSM wall. These findings highlight the importance of considering water content and variations in soil layers when designing and constructing DSM walls. The results also emphasize the need for careful monitoring and analysis during the construction process to mitigate potential settlement issues and ensure the stability and performance of both the DSM wall and adjacent structures.

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